

**FOURFOLD FUNDAMENTAL LINGUISTIC SKILLS PLAY A ROLE OF
PASSPORT TO SUCCESS****Dr.Prashant Kale***Gokhale Education Society's, College of Education & Research, Parel,Mumbai***Asst.Prof. Yogita Bhamre***K.K.Wagh College of Education,Nashik ,Maharashtra,India***Abstract**

The learning of 'English' language has occupied a significant place in our life. The Radhakrishnan Commission (1948-49) observed, "English is a language which is rich in literature. - Humanistic, scientific and technical. English is a window through which we are able to see the scientific, technological, agricultural, commercial and literary developments taking place to the world." Learning a language is not learning about a language. In language learning we have use it, understand the system of that language and finally gain the knowledge of that language. English language teacher get the students acquire the fourfold fundamental linguistic skills – listening, speaking, reading and writing. Any language of the world that is learnt in LSRW sequence or order, that language is learnt properly. It is necessary for the learners to start learning English Primarily through listening. Next the speech is the most important skill that should be nourished to communicate our thoughts and ideas to others. The third skill that is reading – Reading process involves many physical, intellectual and often emotional reactions. Learning writing is one of the productive skills of language. Writing is meant for conveying thoughts, ideas and facts. The key factor of the four basic language skills is that they complement each other. These skills work in pairs. When students listen or read language, they consume it and when they speak or write it they produce language. These fourfold skills are four capabilities that allow an individual to comprehend, produce and use the language in effective interpersonal communication.

Key words- *Language, linguistic skills, listening, speaking, reading, writing, productive*

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Language is a special gift of God to human being. It is language which separates human being from animals. We cannot think or imagine of a society without language. Man, indebted with the power of speaking plays a dominant role in the society over all creatures. It makes him unique. Being the highest creature of God, he utilizes his full potential by the help of language as a means of communication to his fellow members. All other creatures do not have the power to speak and hence cannot compete with human being so far as intellectual, social and emotional development is concerned.

Definition of language.

Jesperon – “Language is a set of human habits, the purpose of which is to give expression to human thoughts and feelings, especially to impart them to others.”

Alen :- “Language is a Social activity rather than a means of individual self-expression”.

Encyclopaedia Britannica:

“Language may be defined as an arbitrary system of vocal symbols by means of which human beings, as a member of social group and participants in culture, interact and communicate”.

(S.S. Panigrahi)

Language plays a vital role in the intellectual development of a person. This is so because language learning is a skill and learning it, the intellect of a person works. When a person learns the words and structures of a new language, his intellectual horizon expands and hence this lead to the development of the person.

(S.S. Panigrahi)

English is one of the most dominating language of the world which is having its impact on every field of work, Undoubtly, English play a much greater role in the world that it is inevitable for people to ignore it fully.

- 1) It is most commonly spoken language in the world.
- 2) It's the language of internationally business.
- 3) English is also essential in the field of education.
- 4) English is the language of the internet and press.
- 5) English is the language of travel and Business.

6) English is the language of Hollywood

English has been playing an important role in our educational system as well as in our national life. English was supreme in the pre-independent India. It was the language of administration, a compulsory subjects at the school and college, and the medium of instruction for some subjects at the school and colleges, and for all subjects at the university level.

In India, English is taught as a foreign language. It is not as a first language but as a second language. Therefore, English is taught for the practical purpose only. Teaching is a process. Any process must tend to a certain direction Teaching a language means performing activities in order to achieve the expected change among the students. Jean Forrester in Teaching without Lecturing stated, 'Learning a language is learning a skill. Skills are learnt only through practice. One acquires them only by doing them, and the more doing'.

(Gurav H.K.)

In learning a language child acquires the ability of understanding others speak, which means, the child starts developing the listening skill. The next, the child tries to reproduce the sound sequence to experts is thoughts and feeling and thus, acquires the skill of speaking. After speaking we introduce the skill of reading. Reading practice from textbook should start after about a few months of aural-oral (listening-speaking) practice. Finally, the language learners need to acquires the skills of writing. That way, as the four skills, namely ,listening ,speaking, reading and writing are required to use the language which is a skill.

1) Teaching Listening

Listening is very basic and important skill of all language skills. The sequence of language skill is not randomly fixed but it is scientifically proved. Any language of the world that is learnt in LSRW sequence or order, that language is learnt properly. Same as our mother tongue if we follow the LSRW sequence to learn English Language we will get the effective results. It is necessary for the learners to start learning English Primarily through listening. If English teachers will implement formulate activities of listening skill, they can develop listening sills of students.

Three main kinds of listening materials that can be used for teaching listening authentic listening materials recorded listening materials live-listening materials

Authentic Materials for Listening Class. Authentic listening materials are recorded live. The

language that is used, not rehearsed. It is not aimed at any specified level of the learners. So, it is difficult for the beginners. Examples for authentic listening materials are, cricket commentary, announcement at the railway station, etc. Recorded Listening Materials. Unlike Authentic Listening Materials, Recorded Listening Materials have been prepared with specific aim and for specific set of learners. These listening materials are supported by worksheets. The students have to solve the worksheets on listening script. For example, in CBSE - course A Interactive in English is supported by two audio cassettes. These types of cassettes or CDs are called Recorded Listening Materials. Live Listening Materials. Here, the teacher himself may be speaking the piece. As the teacher himself asking the piece, he can approach to the listening activity with keeping the level of the students in his mind. So, the students may not have any difficulty over the content and the style of the speaker. The teacher has to possess pronouncing skills with right kind of voice modulation and proper intonation.

Listening Activities

- 1) Authentic, recorded and live.
- 2) BBC world services, edusat
- 3) Materials prepared by RIE, CIEFL etc
- 4) Conversations related to real life situations-natural and spontaneous
- 5) Listen English News
- 7) Listen English Programmer
- 8) Listen speeches of different personalities
- 9) Listen sports commentary in English
- 10) Listen English Songs

2) Teaching of Speaking

Dr. B. Ballard states, "We are ever liable to forget that language is first and foremost a spoken thing, not a written thing. Its appeal is to the ear, not to the eye." In his book Teaching and Testing English Dr. Ballard recommends, "Speech training should have precedence over learning to read, in point of time as well as in point of importance. "So the speech is the most important skill that should be nourished to communicate our thoughts and ideas to others. Learning through speech is the natural way of learning a language.

There are sub skills of speaking:-

1. Producing English speech sounds and sound patterns, both in isolation and in combination.
2. Ability to use appropriate stress and intonation patterns.
3. Use apt words and structures to express the intended meaning.
4. Retrieve or recall words and structures quickly.
5. Organise one's thoughts and ideas in logical sequence.
6. Ability to adjust one's speech according to his audience, situation and subject-matter.

Activities to develop speaking skill

- 1) Short Talks
- 2) Story telling
- 3) Discussion and Debate
- 4) Dialogues and Role Play
- 5) Simulations
- 6) Interviews
- 7) Brain storming

3) Teaching Reading

Michael West says "The sum total of the matter is that before beginning to teach child to read a foreign language it is necessary that he should be made fully efficient in the reading of his mother tongue." Teacher should create the taste for reading among students. Reading process involves many physical, intellectual and often emotional reactions. Further it entails the ability to recognize graphic symbols and their corresponding vocal sounds. Thus, reading skill consists of three important components

- 1) Recognition of the graphic marks
- 2) The correlation of these formal linguistic elements
- 3) The correlation of these with meaning.

Types of Reading

1. Loud reading
2. Silent reading
3. Intensive reading
4. Extensive reading
5. Supplementary reading

6. Library reading

Activities to develop reading

- 1) Reading aloud task in pairs and groups
- 2) Annotate and highlight the text
- 3) Read daily newspaper
- 4) Read text and task
- 5) Read jokes
- 6) Read literature to enrich vocabulary

4) Teaching Writing

Writing is one of four skills (LSRW) in languages. Learning writing is one of the productive skills of language. Writing is meant for conveying thoughts, ideas and facts. It is a system of written symbols syllables or words of language, with different mechanisms, capitalization, spelling and punctuation, word form and function. Writing is very important that communication is transmitted more through writing. So students need effective writing skills to meet their academic needs and workplace requirements. It's the responsibility of teacher to motivate students to improve their writing skill.

Activities to develop writing skill

- 1) Guided writing – story writing
- 2) Essay writing
- 3) Dialogue writing
- 4) Role play writing
- 5) Article Writing
- 6) Note making and note taking
- 7) Letter writing
- 8) Email writing

The key factor of the four basic language skills is that they complement each other. These skills work in pairs. When students listen or read language, they consume it and when they speak or write it they produce language. These fourfold skills are four capabilities that allow an individual to comprehend, produce and use the language in effective interpersonal communication. The skills of language will make the students academically strong and sound.

The four skills never stand out as individual area but they form a chain cycle. If you disturb any one of it the whole chain would collapse. In this competitive world your command over language and even more level of English can determine your life.

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